

STUDIES ON THE PHOTOCHEMICAL ACTIVITY OF
MIXTURES OF VANADIC ACID AND TARTARIC ACID.
PART I. OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF MIXTURES OF
VANADIC ACID AND TARTARIC ACID.
REDUCTION OF THESE MIXTURES IN
LIGHT AND IN THE DARK.

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The relationship between the hydrogen ion concentration and (i) optical rotation, (ii) light absorption and (iii) dark reaction of mixtures of vanadic and tartaric acids has been investigated. The reduction of vanadic acid by racemic-tartaric acid in the dark has been found to give a higher value for the velocity of the reaction than that for the reduction by *d*-, or *l*-, or *dl*-tartaric acids, at the same hydrogen ion concentration. The photoreduction of mixtures of vanadic acid and tartaric acid has been studied in the visible and ultraviolet regions.

Biltz (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 1098) found that the reddish brown product obtained by the addition of dilute hydrochloric acid to ammonium metavanadate gives a reddish yellow colloidal solution of vanadium pentoxide on being washed with distilled water. Dumansky (*Kolloid Z.*, 1923, 33, 147), found that the red sol of vanadic acid contains negatively charged particles, and postulated that by the addition of hydrochloric acid to salts of orthovanadic acid, the following changes occur :

i.e. with progressive increase in the number of atoms of vanadium in a molecule of vanadic acid, the colloid chemical properties become more and more manifest. Dumansky (*loc. cit.*) has also shown that the pentoxide sols on being treated with reducing agents furnish the sols of lower oxides of vanadium which are also negatively charged.

Vanadic acid sol displays peculiar optical phenomena. Freundlich *et al* (*Koll.-chem. Beih.*, 1915, 7, 195 ; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, 114, 161) have studied the phenomena of streaming double refraction and dichroism in vanadic acid sol. Reinders (*Proc. K. Akad. Wetensch. Amsterdam*, 1916, 19, 189) showed that a freshly prepared colloidal solution is not birefringent ; on keeping it slowly develops double refraction due to the formation of needle-shaped micro-crystalline micelles. Kruyt (*Kolloid Z.*, 1916, 19, 16) concluded that the orientation was due to the cataphoretic motion of rod-shaped particles. Marshall (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 173) has

studied the electrical double refraction of a 6-year old sol and has shown that the orientation of anisotropic particles depends primarily on their fundamental electrical properties. Lange (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 132, 21) studied the polarisation of the Tyndall light from the sol and concluded that the particles were not spherical in shape. Zocher and Jacobsohn (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 41, 220) showed that some sols of vanadium pentoxide spontaneously separate into two phases—one is isotropic and dilute, the other anisotropic and concentrated.

Vanadic acid becomes markedly photo-sensitive when exposed to light with organic substances like tartaric acid, glycerol, benzaldehyde, etc. It blackens and undergoes reduction, giving rise initially to the tetroxide (Gibbons, *Chem. News*, 1874, 30, 267, 1874; Renz, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, 4, 961).

In the present investigation, the optical and photochemical properties of vanadium compounds have been studied in the p_H range 1.4 to 6.6 where vanadic acid exists either as polyvanadic acid sol or as vanadate.

A. Optical Properties of Mixtures of Vanadic Acid and Optically Active Tartaric Acid at low p_H .

(a) *Optical Rotation.*—When *d*- or *l*-tartaric acid is added to sodium metavanadate ($\text{NaVO}_3 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$), the mixture has an optical rotation which is *opposite* in sign to the rotation of the tartaric acid used. It was found that an addition of hydrochloric acid to this mixture, *i.e.*, increase in $[\text{H}^+]$, the rotation gradually decreased. The relationship between the rotation and the $[\text{H}^+]$ of the mixture was studied by using equimolecular mixtures of vanadic and tartaric acids at p_H 4, and increasing the $[\text{H}^+]$ by addition of hydrochloric or tartaric acids, keeping the final concentration of the mixture the same in each case.

The changes in the rotation of the mixture were followed in yellow light with a Winkel-Zeiss triple-field polarimeter which gave readings to $\pm 0.01^\circ$. The measurements were made in the shortest possible time in order to avoid the error that is likely to be introduced due to the dark reaction at very low p_H . The chemicals used were all either Merck's or Kahlbaum's samples, and tartaric acids were recrystallised before use. 'conductivity water' was used throughout for preparing the solutions. The p_H of the mixtures was measured by means of the glass electrode. The results obtained by adding hydrochloric acid to an equimolar mixture of vanadic acid and *d*-tartaric acid are given below. The concentration of vanadate is always given as amount of pentavalent vanadium.

TABLE I.

Length of solution (d) = 2.5 cm. $\lambda = 5893\text{\AA}$. Temp. = 25°.

Conc. of vanadium in starting mixture.

[H ⁺]	0.033 M Rotation of Mixture. Free H ₂ T.*	[H ⁺]	0.025 M Rotation of Mixture. Free H ₂ T.*	[H ⁺]	0.017 M Rotation of Mixture. Free H ₂ T.*
1×10^{-4}	-0.18° < +0.02°	1×10^{-4}	-0.12 < +0.02°	1×10^{-4}	-0.08 < +0.01°
25	-0.13	13	-0.10	37	-0.05
50	-0.10	89	-0.05	100	-0.03
75	-0.08	190	-0.03		
130	-0.06				

* H₂T = Tartaric acid.

The results show that the rotation of the mixture is negative and it decreases with increase in [H⁺]. Columns 3, 6 and 9 of the above table give the rotation that should have been observed if all the *d*-tartaric acid were present alone as free molecules in solution. It shows that the magnitude of mixture is much higher than that of free tartaric acid. Some rotation measurements were made by varying the [H⁺] by an increase in the concentration of *d*-tartaric acid. The results are given below :

TABLE II.

Other conditions same as in Table I.

Conc. of <i>d</i> -tartaric acid.	Conc. of vanadium.	[H ⁺].	Rotation of Mixture.	Rotation of Free H ₂ T.
0.025 M	0.025 M	1×10^{-4}	-0.12°	< +0.02°
0.033	"	13	-0.10	< +0.02
0.067	"	89	-0.05	< +0.03
0.100	"	190	-0.03	< +0.05

The results show that if *d*-tartaric acid itself is used to increase the [H⁺] in place of hydrochloric acid, the observed rotations are identical for the same p_{H} , with those given in Table I. Table II, column 5 gives the calculated value of the rotations if the whole of *d*-tartaric acid existed in solution as free molecules.

It is clear that the solution does not contain any free tartaric acid even when the ratio H₂T : NaVO₃ = 4 : 1, but negatively charged poly-vanadic

acid-tartaric acid micelles having the composition $[x.VO_3^-, y.H_2T, z.H^+]$, where x/y is as the ratio of the molar concentrations of vanadate and tartaric acid respectively. These micelles have a negative optical rotation even though *d*-tartaric acid enters into the formation of the colloidal micelle. Again, the magnitude of the rotation is independent of the ratio of x/y , but is dependent on the p_H of the environment and the vanadate content of the solution as will be clear from Table I. We have, therefore, to postulate an ionic adsorption equilibrium of the type

If it is assumed that the micelle with the larger negative charge $[x.VO_3^-.y.H_2T.(z-1)H^+]$ has a negative rotation very much greater than that of the micelle $[x.VO_3^-.y.H_2T.H^+]$ and that the concentration of the former is inversely proportional to the $[H^+]$, the experimental results can be explained almost quantitatively. Fig. 1 (curve 1) shows that the optical rotation of the colloidal micelle is approximately in inverse proportion to the $[H^+]$, indicating that the concentration of the micelle $[x.VO_3^-.y.H_2T.(z-1)H^+]$ is approximately in inverse proportion to the $[H^+]$.

FIG. 1.

When tartaric acid (*d*-, *l*- or τ -) is added to sodium metavanadate, a deep red colour is developed: the mixture has a high extinction coefficient

in blue light. Addition of hydrochloric acid to this mixture resulted in the colour gradually fading to orange, yellow and finally pale yellow, and the light absorption of the mixture decreased. This decrease in light absorption runs parallel with the decrease in rotation. The relationship between the absorption and the $[H^+]$ was studied according to the method described for rotation measurements. The absorption was measured by the König-Martens spectrophotometer which was calibrated for $4916\text{\AA}$, the wavelength in which the readings were taken. The results obtained by increasing the $[H^+]$ of equimolar mixtures of *d*-tartaric acid and vanadate at p_H 4 by the addition of hydrochloric acid, are given below.

TABLE III.

Length of solution (*d*) = 0.5 cm. $\lambda = 4916\text{\AA}$. Temp. = 25°.
Conc. of starting mixture.

0.033 M.		0.025 M.		0.017 M.	
$[H^+]$	$\epsilon, c, d.$ *	$[H^+]$	$\epsilon, c, d.$	$[H^+]$	$\epsilon, c, d.$
1×10^{-4}	0.62	1×10^{-4}	0.47	1×10^{-4}	0.29
20	0.47	21	0.36	20	0.22
63	0.32	91	0.19	100	0.11
130	0.20	210	0.11	280	0.05
250	0.12	350	0.07		

* ϵ = Extinction coeff. C = Conc.

The absorption decreases with increase in $[H^+]$ of the mixture. The value of the extinction coefficient, like the optical rotation, simply depends on the p_H and the vanadate content of the solution. Table IV shows that similar results are obtained if *d*-tartaric acid is used to increase the $[H^+]$ in place of hydrochloric acid.

TABLE IV.

Other conditions same as in Table III.

Conc. of <i>d</i> -H ₂ T.	Conc. of vanadium ₅	$[H^+]$.	$\epsilon, c, d.$
0.033 M	0.033 M	1×10^{-4}	0.62
0.050	"	20	0.47
0.083	"	79	0.28
0.125	"	140	0.19
0.167	"	360	0.09

The experimental observations on the extinction coefficients of polyvanadic acid-tartaric acid micelles lend support to the assumptions made in explaining the observed optical rotations of such micelles. In the adsorption

equilibrium equation (i) the more negatively charged micelle $[x.VO_3^-y.H_2T. (z-1)H^+]$ is red-orange in colour and has a high extinction coefficient in blue light. As the $[H^+]$ is increased, the colour fades from yellow to pale yellow, the extinction coefficient decreases and we have the less negatively charged micelle $[x.VO_3^-.y.H_2T. z.H^+]$. Fig. 1 (curve 2) shows that like the optical rotation, the light absorption of the colloidal micelle is approximately in inverse proportion to $[H^+]$; this indicates that the concentration of the micelle $[x.VO_3^-y.H_2T. (z-1) H^+]$ is approximately in inverse proportion to the $[H^+]$.

Experiments with d-, l-, and r-Acids.

Some experiments on the optical rotation and light absorption of vanadic acid-tartaric acid mixtures were carried out with *l*- and racemic tartaric acids. The results showed that mixtures of *d*- and *l*-acids with vanadic acid give rotations which are equal in magnitude but opposite in sign, at the same $[H^+]$. Again, a mixture containing *d*- or *l*-acid has a rotation which is opposite in sign to the rotation of the free tartaric acid. A mixture of racemic acid and vanadic acid has no rotation.

In absorption measurements, no difference was obtained for the absorption of mixtures containing *d*-, *l*-, or *r*-acids, at the same $[H^+]$.

B. Reduction of Mixtures of Vanadic Acid and Tartaric Acid in the Dark at low p_H .

Detailed investigation of the effect of p_H on the reduction of penta-valent vanadium by tartaric acid (from polyvanadic acid sol to polyvanadous acid sol) in the dark showed that, for all mixtures of tartaric acid and sodium vanadate, there is a definite $p_H = 4$, above which there is no dark reaction; below this p_H , the dark reaction proceeds, its velocity increasing with decreasing p_H i.e., increasing $[H^+]$ of the mixture. It was shown in Sec. A that an increase in the $[H^+]$ of vanadic acid-tartaric acid mixtures results in a decrease in the optical rotation and light absorption. These changes are simultaneously accompanied by an increase in the velocity of the dark reaction.

The reaction was followed by estimating the vanadium according to the method of Furman (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1925, 17, 314). The mixture to be estimated was titrated in sulphuric acid solution (final acid concentration being 30 c.c. acid of sp. gr. 1.84 in 1 litre) with ferrous sulphate using a freshly prepared 0.1% sulphuric acid solution of diphenylamine as indicator.

The effect of variation of the $[H^+]$ on the velocity of the reaction was studied by varying the concentration of *d*-tartaric acid, keeping the

initial concentration of vanadate (as pentavalent vanadium) constant. Table V below gives the observed values of the velocity. The value of dx/dt is given as the number of g. mols transformed per minute at the beginning of the reaction.

TABLE V.

Temp. = 25°.

Conc. of $d\text{-H}_2\text{T}$. Vanadium. $[\text{H}^+]$.			$\frac{dx}{dt}$.	Conc. of $d\text{-H}_2\text{T}$. Vanadium. $[\text{H}^+]$.			$\frac{dx}{dt}$.
0.033 M	0.033 M	1×10^{-4}	—	0.063	0.025	57×10^{-6}	122×10^{-6}
0.050	"	20	78×10^{-6}	0.083	"	120	160
0.067	"	50	162	0.100	"	190	187
0.083	"	79	189	0.125	"	220	200
0.100	"	89	205	0.017	0.017	1	—
0.125	"	140	240	0.025	"	9	20
0.167	"	360	290	0.033	"	33	55
0.025	0.025	1	—	0.050	"	60	81
0.031	"	7	24	0.056	"	79	94
0.050	"	28	75	0.083	"	180	125

The velocity of the reaction increases with increase in $[\text{H}^+]$. The effect of variation of $[\text{H}^+]$ on the velocity was also studied by the addition of hydrochloric acid to an equimolar mixture of vanadic acid and tartaric acid. The results are given below.

TABLE VI.

Temp. = 25°.

Concentration of vanadium in starting mixture

0.050 M		0.033 M		0.025 M		0.017 M	
$[\text{H}^+]$.	dx/dt .	$[\text{H}^+]$.	dx/dt	$[\text{H}^+]$.	dx/dt .	$[\text{H}^+]$.	dx/dt .
1×10^{-4}	—	1×10^{-4}	—	1×10^{-4}	—	1×10^{-4}	—
3	19×10^{-6}	14	62×10^{-6}	14	46×10^{-6}	14×10^{-6}	31
14	92	50	162	50	122	50	81
50	243	79	189	200	187	200	125
200	375	200	250				

Tables V and VI clearly show that it does not matter whether *d*-tartaric acid or hydrochloric acid is used to increase the $[H^+]$; the result is the same. The velocity of the dark reaction, like the optical rotation and light absorption, depends only upon the p_n and the vanadium content of the solution. In fact, the value of dx/dt , at the same p_n , is directly proportional to the concentration of vanadium (Table VI).

It appears that the hypothesis of ionic adsorption equilibrium for polyvanadic acid-tartaric acid micelles, which could reasonably explain the optical properties of such micelles, can also explain the experimental results on the dark reaction. Colloidal micelles of the type $[x.VO_3^- \cdot y.H_2T \cdot z.H^+]$ exist in equilibrium with the hydrogen ions in the solution, and the equation for the adsorption equilibrium is

The more negatively charged micelle $[x.VO_3^- \cdot y.H_2T \cdot (z-1)H^+]$ does not undergo reduction in the dark at p_n equal to and greater than 4. As the $[H^+]$ is increased, the velocity of the dark reaction gradually increases and we have the micelle $[x.VO_3^- \cdot y.H_2T \cdot z.H^+]$, which is responsible for the reduction in the dark. Fig. 1 (curve 3) in Sec. A shows that, whereas the optical rotation and light absorption are approximately in inverse proportion to the $[H^+]$, the velocity of the dark reaction is approximately proportional to the $[H^+]$. This means that the concentration of the micelle $[x.VO_3^- \cdot y.H_2T \cdot z.H^+]$ is approximately proportional to the $[H^+]$.

Dark Reaction with d-, l-, dl- and r-Acids.

It is usually held that racemic compounds only exist in the crystalline condition and that when they are dissolved they dissociate into simple mixtures of two externally compensated optical isomers, (Jaeger, "Le Principe de Symetric et ses Applications," Paris, p. 245). On the other hand, Cotton (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 377) has pointed out to the distinction that must be made between the solution of a racemate and simple mixture which is inactive by external compensation. From his observations on the differences in light absorption of alkaline solutions of copper racemate and *d*- or *l*-tartrate, Cotton (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1896, 8, 347) concludes that there are some racemic compounds which can be dissolved without complete dissociation. Similar results have been obtained by Gabiano (*Compt. rend.*, 1927, 184, 1059) and De Malleman and Gabiano (*ibid.*, 1927, 185, 350) with copper racemate and tartrate solutions.

In the present investigation, the reduction of a mixture of vanadic acid and racemic-tartaric acid in the dark gave a higher value, at the same

p_H , for the velocity than that for *d*-tartaric acid, whereas the *l*-acid as well as the *dl*-mixture (mixture of *d*- and *l*-acids in equimolar proportions) gave the same velocity as *d*-acid. The results obtained are given below.

TABLE VII.

Temp. = 25°.

Concentration of H ₂ T.	Concentration of Vanadium.	[H ⁺].	$dx/dt \times 10^6$.			
			<i>d</i> -H ₂ T.	<i>r</i> -H ₂ T.	<i>l</i> -H ₂ T.	<i>dl</i> -H ₂ T.
0.167 M	0.033 M	360×10^{-4}	290	370	290	290
0.125	"	140	240	304		
0.100	"	89	205	270		
0.083	"	79	180	239		
0.050	"	20	78	103	80	78
0.125	0.025	220	200	255	200	202
0.100	"	190	187	237		
0.083	"	120	160	199		
0.063	"	57	122	160		
0.050	"	28	75	104	75	75
0.031	"	7	24	34		
0.083	0.017	180	125	161	122	125
0.056	"	79	94	132		
0.050	"	60	81	100	81	81
0.033	"	33	55	80		
0.025	"	9	20	30		

The differences in velocity that are obtained with racemic-acid are very large (between 25 to 50%). It appears peculiar that the racemic-acid mixture should give a higher value for the velocity whereas the *dl*-mixture gives the same value as that for *d*- or *l*-acid. It is probable that the colloidal micelle of racemic-acid and vanadic acid is different from that of the micelle containing *d*- or *l*- or *dl*-acids.

C. Photoreduction of Mixtures of Sodium Vanadate and Tartaric Acid at p_H greater than 4.

A mixture of vanadic acid and tartaric acid is photosensitive to ultraviolet as well as to visible light, and undergoes photoreduction :

the colour change being from red or yellow to greenish-black, blue or violet, depending upon the p_H . At low p_H , the dark reaction is rapid, and the photochemical reaction is small. As the p_H is increased the light reaction

becomes more appreciable, and at p_{H} , 4 the dark reaction disappears and only the photoreaction proceeds.

The kinetics of the photoreduction has been studied in the ultraviolet, blue and green regions. The vanadium content (in the pentavalent state) of the mixture was estimated as before.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The source of light was a quartz-mercury arc lamp which was run from a battery of 220 volts, at a constant current of 1.6 amperes. Light from the lamp was rendered parallel by means of quartz cylindrical lenses and passed into the reaction vessel kept inside a double-jacketed box, which was maintained at constant temperature by circulating water from a thermostat through its annular space. The reaction vessel was a rectangular stoppered cell (1.8 cm. $\times$ 1.8 cm. $\times$ 0.5 cm.) made of plane parallel plates of fused transparent quartz, the joints being fused to one another. The following filters were used to isolate the required monochromatic radiations:

3130Å	...	Ultraviolet filter, (Chance Bros.)
4360Å	...	Zeiss monochromatic filter
5460Å	...	„ „ „

In addition, water or 1% CuSO_4 filters were used to cut off the infra-red radiation.

The intensity of the incident radiation was varied by using lenses of different focal lengths. The thickness of the cell was on purpose made as small as possible so that the liquid inside may be considered to have a practically homogeneous light intensity in different layers. The intensity of the absorbed radiation was measured by means of a Moll thermopile and Moll galvanometer. The thermopile was frequently calibrated by means of a standard lamp supplied by the Bureau of Standards. The absorbed intensity was determined by observing the galvanometer deflections with water and then with the reaction mixture in the cell. During the measurements, the thermopile was always placed at the same position, immediately behind the reaction cell.

Above p_{H} 4 tartaric acid is mostly dissociated into HT^- ion, and equimolecular complex ions of the type $[\text{VO}_3^-, \text{HT}^-]$ appear to exist in solution. Even in the p_{H} region 4.3 to 6.6, the vanadate-*d*-tartaric acid mixture has a negative optical rotation, the value being as high as -0.18° at p_{H} 5.3. The photoreduction of such mixtures was studied, with the concentration of vanadate greater than that of tartaric acid in all cases, i.e. concentration of equimolar complex ion is equal to concentration of

tartaric acid. It is clear that there is no free tartaric acid in solution, but only free vanadate ions in all these mixtures.

The reaction was studied in the visible as well as in the ultraviolet. It is zero molecular with respect to vanadate (pentavalent vanadium) and there is no dark reaction. Table VIII gives the effect of varying the concentration of the reactants on the velocity of the photoreduction. *d*-Tartaric acid has been used and dx/dt refers to the number of g. mols transformed per minute.

Reaction in the Ultraviolet.

TABLE VIII.

Effect of varying the concentration.

$\lambda = 3130\text{\AA}$. Temp. = 28° . $p_H = 4.3$ to 5.7 . $I_{\text{abs.}} = 10294$ ergs for all the mixtures.

$$(dx/dt) = I_{\text{abs.}} \times 5.38 \times 10^{-7} \times \frac{\text{Conc. of equimol. complex ion}}{1 + (18.5 \times \text{conc. of free vanadate ion})}$$

Concentration of H_2T .		$dx/dt \times 10^6$		Concentration of H_2T .		$dx/dt \times 10^6$	
NaVO_3 .		Obs.	Calc.	NaVO_3 .		Obs.	Calc.
0.050 M	0.100 M	14.1	14.4	0.025 M	0.33 M	10.8	12.0
0.025	0.050	9.2	9.5	0.017	"	7.2	7.1
0.017	0.033	7.1	7.1	0.013	"	5.3	5.0
0.013	0.025	5.9	5.6	0.010	"	4.0	3.9
0.008	0.017	4.3	4.0	0.008	"	3.3	3.2
				0.006	"	2.4	2.3
0.017	0.025	8.0	8.0	0.013	0.017	6.5	6.4
0.013	"	5.9	5.6	0.010	"	5.0	4.9
0.008	"	3.6	3.5	0.008	"	4.3	4.0
0.006	"	2.5	2.6	0.006	"	3.2	3.0
0.004	"	1.8	1.7	0.004	"	1.9	1.9

The velocity of the reaction decreases with decrease in equimolar concentration.

The effect of varying the intensity of the absorbed radiation of the velocity of the reaction is given below.

TABLE IX.

Effect of varying the intensity of the absorbed radiation.

$\lambda = 3130\text{\AA}$. Temp. = 28° . $p_H = 5.2$.

Conc. of H_2T	Conc. of NaVO_3 .	$I_{\text{abs.}}$	dx/dt .
0.050 M	0.100 M	10294 ergs.	14.1×10^{-6}
"	"	4428	6.3
"	"	1125	1.6
0.025	0.050	10294	9.2
"	"	4498	4.0

For the same mixture, the value of dx/dt is proportional to $I_{\text{abs.}}$

Reaction in the Blue.

TABLE X.

Effect of varying the concentration. $\lambda = 4360 \text{ \AA}$. $I_{\text{abs.}} = 7440$ ergs for all mixtures. Temp. = 28° . $p_{\text{H}} = 5.3$ to 6.6 . $dx/dt =$ same as in Table VIII.

Concentration of H_2T .		$dx/dt \times 10^6$		Concentration of NaVO_3		$dx/dt \times 10^6$	
H_2T .	NaVO_3 .	Obs.	Calc.	H_2T .	NaVO_3	Obs.	Calc.
0.125 M	0.250 M	15.3	15.1	0.125 M	0.250 M	15.3	15.1
0.083	0.167	12.8	13.0	0.083	"	8.5	8.2
0.050	0.100	10.2	10.3	0.063	"	6.1	5.7
0.025	0.050	7.0	7.0	0.050	"	4.8	4.3
0.017	0.033	5.5	5.6	0.025	"	2.2	2.0
0.013	0.025	4.2	4.1				
0.050	0.100	10.2	10.3	0.025	0.050	7.0	7.0
0.033	"	5.7	5.9	0.017	"	4.5	4.1
0.025	"	4.2	4.2	0.013	"	3.2	3.0
0.017	"	2.8	2.6	0.008	"	2.3	2.0
0.013	"	2.1	2.0	0.006	"	1.5	1.4

The above results are of the same type as those obtained for the reaction in the ultraviolet, the velocity of the reaction decreasing with decreasing equimolar concentration. Table XI shows that the velocity of the reaction in blue light is proportional to the intensity of the light absorbed.

TABLE XI.

Effect of varying the absorbed intensity. $\lambda = 4360 \text{ \AA}$. Temp. = 28° . $p_{\text{H}} = 5.2$

Conc. of H_2T .	Conc. of NaVO_3 .	$I_{\text{abs.}}$	dx/dt .
0.125 M	0.250 M	7440 erg.	15.3×10^{-6}
"	"	5017	10.0
"	"	3720	7.7
0.050	0.100	7440	10.2
"	"	3720	5.1

Reaction in the Green

The photoreduction in the green region gave the following results.

TABLE XII.

Effect of varying the concentration.

$\lambda = 5460\text{\AA}$. Temp. = 28°. $p_H = 5.4$ to 6.6.

$$(dx/dt) = I_{abs.} \times 2.89 \times 10^{-7} \times \frac{\text{conc. of equimol. complex ion.}}{1 + (18.5 \times \text{conc. of free vanadate ion})}$$

Conc. of H_2T .	Conc. of $NaVO_3$.	$I_{abs.}$	$dx/dt \times 10^6$.	
			obs.	calc.
0.125 M	0.250 M	7698 ergs.	8.5	8.4
0.083	0.167	7577	7.2	7.2
0.050	0.100	7440	5.6	5.6
0.025	0.050	6747	3.2	3.3
0.017	0.033	5882	2.2	2.2
0.125	0.250	7698	8.5	8.4
0.083	"	"	4.4	4.5
0.050	"	"	2.5	2.4
0.031	"	"	1.4	1.4
0.025	"	"	1.1	1.1
0.083	0.167	7577	7.2	7.2
0.056	"	"	3.6	3.8
0.042	"	"	2.7	2.7
0.028	"	"	1.6	1.7
0.021	"	"	1.3	1.3

TABLE XIII.

Effect of varying the absorbed intensity.

$\lambda = 5460\text{\AA}$. Temp. = 28°. $p_H = 5.2$.

Conc. of H_2T .	Conc. of $NaVO_3$.	$I_{abs.}$	dx/dt
0.125 M	0.250 M	7698 ergs.	7.5×10^{-8}
"	"	5363	5.0
"	"	3892	3.7
0.083	0.167	7577	6.0
"	"	5363	4.2

Table XII shows that the value of dx/dt decreases with decrease in equimolar concentration. Table XIII shows that the velocity is proportional to I_{abs} .

Reaction with d-, l- and r-Acids.

Some experiments were carried out wherein *l*- and *r*-tartaric acids were the photo-active reductants. The results given in Table XIV below show that there is no difference in the velocity of the photoreduction with these acids in all the wave-lengths studied. The dark reaction, on the other hand, gave a higher value for the velocity with racemic acid as reductant.

TABLE XIV.

$p_{\text{H}} = 5.2$. Temp. = 21° . I_{abs} . is the same for mixtures of *d*-, *l*- or racemic-acids.

Wave-length (λ).	Concentration of		I_{abs} .	$dx/dt \times 10^5$.		
	H_2T .	NaVO_3 .		<i>d</i> - H_2T .	<i>l</i> - H_2T .	<i>r</i> - H_2T .
3130 $\text{\AA}$	0.050 <i>M</i>	0.100 <i>M</i>	10294 ergs	14.1	14.1	14.3
"	0.025	0.050	"	9.2	9.1	9.2
"	0.017	0.033	"	7.1	7.1	7.2
4360	0.050	0.100	7440	10.2	10.2	10.3
"	0.025	0.050	"	7.0	7.0	7.0
5460	0.050	0.100	"	5.6	5.7	5.7
"	0.025	0.050	6747	3.2	3.2	3.2

Temperature coefficient.—The temperature Coefficient (35° – 25°) of the reaction is very small, being of the order 1.02–1.12 in the wave-lengths in which the reaction was carried out.

Quantum Efficiency of the Process.—The quantum efficiency of the photo-process in the various wave-lengths is given below :

TABLE XV.

Temp. = 28° . $p_{\text{H}} = 5.2$.

Conc. of H_2T .	Conc. of NaVO_3 .	Quantum efficiency (η).		
		3130 $\text{\AA}$	4360 $\text{\AA}$	5460 $\text{\AA}$
0.050 <i>M</i>	0.100 <i>M</i>	0.44	0.31	0.14
0.025	0.050	0.28	0.22	0.09
0.017	0.035	0.22	0.17	0.07

The value of γ decreases with increasing wave length of the radiation ; and for the same wave length, it decreases with decreasing equimolar concentration.

DISCUSSION.

The photoreduction of mixtures of sodium vanadate and tartaric acid, at p_H greater than 4, has the following characteristic features:

(i) The velocity of the reaction decreases with decrease in the concentration of the equimolar complex ion. (ii) The temperature coefficient is small. (iii) The quantum efficiency varies between 0.44 and 0.07. (iv) The velocity of the reaction is proportional to the intensity of the absorbed radiation. (v) $\frac{I_{obs.} \times \text{conc. of equimolar complex ion}}{dx/dt}$ when plotted against

concentration of free vanadate ion gives a straight line (Fig. 2).

The following mechanism can explain the main features of the photo-reduction: (The term 'complex' refers to an equimolar complex ion of the type $\text{VO}_3^- \cdot \text{HT}^-$).

If k_1 , k_2 and k_3 are the velocity constants for the processes (i), (ii) and (iii) respectively, we have, for the velocity of the reaction the equation

$$dx/dt = I_{abs} \times \frac{k_1 \times \text{conc. of equimolar complex ion}}{1 + [(k_2/k_3) \times \text{conc. of free vanadate ion}]}$$

i.e.
$$\frac{I_{abs} \times \text{conc. of equimolar complex ion}}{dx/dt}$$

when plotted against concentration of free vanadate ion should give a straight line, as is actually the case. There is good agreement between the observed values of the velocity and those calculated from the above equation, wherein k_1 , and k_2/k_3 have the values given in the above tables.

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